

Paper ID: NITETE&TC02

ELECTRICITY MANAGEMENT IN SMART CITY USING RASPBERRY PI

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ABSTRACT

Raspberry Pi is latest technology having lot of application in real world. The best part is high technology with low cost. This technology is utilized for automation of public light system viz. garden light, street light. The project deals with the issue caused due to under utilization of resources and also overcome the irregularities of common workers (staff). The implemented system has 2 facilities like:

- (1) Light will be turned ON only during dark hours (6pm to 6am).
- (2) During less traffic or less people in garden i.e. very less movement for this light intensity is controlled either by dimming them or alternate turning OFF.

With availability of advanced features with Raspberry Pi the project further can be improved with advanced feature inclusion.

KEYWORDS – Lightening automation, Standby Power reduction.

INTRODUCTION

The Smart City paradigm helps renovate the traditional city concept. In fact, it is possible to realize and develop efficient demand-side strategies integrating the monitoring and automation features. Enabled by intelligent devices and their communication apparatus typically used in many applications.

Within this concept, public lighting, being a great electrical energy consumer, has recently been attracting the interest of the research community. Scientists, combining the Smart City paradigm with alternative energies and new lighting technologies, are conceiving systems previously unimaginable, we are proposing the system for efficient utilization using Raspberry Pi which can increase the efficiency obtaining considerable energy consumption savings and consequently money savings.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In this area, the efforts are focused on the use of alternative energies for the power supply of new lighting technologies, which allow obtaining considerable energy savings. Within lighting technologies, Light Emitting Diodes (LEDs) assure the possibility of switching on the lamp without the preheating typical of halogen ones; a very high lighting efficiency; low power consumption; a superior life time and quick switching times not comparable to those of older technologies (only incandescent lights have a lower lighting time, but with very big power consumption and the shortest time life); less sensitivity to transient phenomena, which have a big impact on other technologies, allowing thousands of lightings without the risk of lamp failure.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

To use the technology to enhance the electricity management for city with effective lighting system using automation in areas like street light, Public places viz Gardens, Government offices etc.

BLOCK DIAGRAM

R-PI BOARD

Board Name: - Raspberry Pi 2, Model B The Raspberry Pi 2 delivers 6 times the processing capacity of previous models. This second generation Raspberry Pi has an upgraded Broadcom BCM2836 processor, which is a powerful ARM Cortex-A7 based quad-core processor that runs at 900MHz. The board also features an increase in memory capacity to 1Gbyte.

RASPBERRY PI MODEL

SPECIFICATIONS

Chip	Broadcom BCM2836 SoC
Core architecture	Quad-core ARM Cortex-A7 900MHz
CPU	Dual Core VideoCore IV Multimedia Co-Processor
GPU	Dual Core VideoCore IV® Multimedia Co-Processor Provides Open GL ES 2.0, hardware-accelerated OpenVG, and 1080p30 H.264 high-profile decode Capable of 1Gpixel/s, 1.5Gtexel/s or 24GFLOPs with texture filtering and DMA infrastructure
Memory	1GB LPDDR2
Operating System	Boots from Micro SD card, running a version of the Linux operating system
Dimension	85 x 56 x 17mm
Power	Micro USB socket 5V, 2A

CONNECTORS

Ethernet	10/100 BaseT Ethernet socket
Video Output	HDMI (rev 1.3 & 1.4)
Audio Output	3.5mm jack, HDMI
USB	4 x USB 2.0 Connector
GPIO Connector	40-pin 2.54 mm (100 mil) expansion header: 2x20 strip Providing 27 GPIO pins as well as +3.3 V, +5 V and GND supply lines
Camera Connector	15-pin MIPI Camera Serial Interface (CSI-2)
JTAG	Not populated
Display Connector	Display Serial Interface (DSI) 15 way flat flex cable connector with two data lanes and a clock lane
Memory Card Slot	Micro SDIO

CONCLUSION

It is proposed to implement the Project using Raspberry pi Technology as it is Emerging Technology and in coming near future most of the equipment and control systems will be connected to internet using Internet of things this will help to further enhance our project usefulness.

REFERENCES

1. Elejoste, P.; Angulo, I.; Perallos, A.; Chertudi, A.; GarcíaZuazola, I.J.; Moreno, A.; Azpilicueta, L.; Astrain, J.J.; Falcone, F.; Villadangos, J. An Easy to Deploy Street Light Control System Based on Wireless Communication and LED Technology. Sensors 2013.

2. Tan, Y.K.; Huynh, T.P.; Wang, Z. Smart Personal Sensor Network Control for Energy Saving in DC Grid Powered LED Lighting System. IEEE Trans. Smart Grid 2013.

3. Magazine of "Electronics for you"(2014).

4. www.electronic hub.com

5. <http://www.raspberrypi.org>

IDEA OF IMPLEMENTATION

